

Chemical Examination of the Marking-nut (*Semecarpus Anacardium*, Linn).

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Semecarpus anacardium, Linn (Hindi, *Bhilawan*, English, Marking-nut) grows in the tropical outer Himalayas and the hotter parts of India. Dymock ("Pharmacographia Indica", Vol. I. p. 389, and Kirtikar and Basu ("Indian Medicinal Plants", Vol. I. p. 384) may be referred to for the details of its history and uses. It may, however, be stated here that the black corrosive juice of the pericarp of the nut, which raises painful blisters on the skin but whose internal administration in dilution with emollient oils is considered safe in fairly large doses, has been found to be of great medicinal value, internally in cases of rheumatism, epilepsy, nervous debility, piles and dyspepsia, externally for eczema, lepra and several other diseases of the skin. It is also used by *dhobis* as an indelible marking ink in admixture with lime.

In spite of its enormous therapeutical significance, the chemical work done on the drug was limited to a conjecture ("Pharmacographia Indica," Vol. I. p. 392) that the tarry oil of its pericarp must be similar to that obtained from the pericarp of cashew nut (*Anacardium occidentale*), which consists of about 90 per cent. of an oxy-acid named anacardic acid, $C_{22}H_{32}O_3$ (Ruhemann and Skinner, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 1861; also *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1887, 51, 663) and 10 per cent. of a higher, non-volatile alcohol called cardol, $C_{21}H_{30}O_2$ (Stadeler, *Annalen*, 1847, 63, 137) and an investigation by Naidu (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1928, 8A, 129), who claims to have isolated from it catechol and a monohydroxyphenol, $C_{18}H_{30}O$, which he called anacardol, besides two acids, and a fixed oil from the kernel of the nut.

As a result of our investigations we have succeeded in establishing that neither anacardic acid and cardol nor catechol and anacardol are present in *Bhilawan*, and have isolated the following products from the black juice of the pericarp, of which we obtained 28 to 36 per cent. on the weight of the nut as against 21 to 25 per cent. got by Naidu (*loc. cit.*).

1. A monohydroxyphenol, which boils at 185-90°/2.5 mm. congeals below 25° to a fatty mass, forms 0.1 per cent. of the extract, and to which we have given the name "Semecarpol."

2. An *o*-dihydroxy-compound, $C_{21}H_{32}O_2$, which distils constantly at 225-26°/3 mm., congeals below 5°, and forms 46 per cent. of the juice (15 to 17 per cent. of the nut). We have called it "Bhilawanol."

3. A tarry corrosive residue, out of which no further chemical individual could be isolated even after repeated purification by means of solution in dilute alcohol and precipitation with alcoholic lead acetate.

Apart from the isolation and investigation of these products we also examined the alcoholic extract of the pericarp, after its exhaustion with ether and the ethereal extract of the kernel. The former was found to contain an ether-soluble and an ether-insoluble acid besides tannic acid, and the latter, 32.3 per cent. of a fatty oil; but as these products did not appear to be of any therapeutical interest they were not studied further.

Constitution of Bhilawanol.—From the analysis of bhilawanol and the determination of its molecular weight, bromine value and hydroxyl groups we fixed on the molecular formula, $C_{21}H_{32}O_2$. That catechol formed the nucleus of bhilawanol was suggested by its colour reactions and supported by the isolation of catechol from the products of its dry distillation. The diacetyl, dibenzoyl, and dimethyl ether derivatives of bhilawanol were prepared and gave analytical results answering to the formula mentioned below, but none of them formed a solid. Of the other derivatives it was possible to get

only the naphthylurethane as a solid, melting at 138-40° which, however, could not be crystallised. On hydrogenation of bhilawanol with the help of platinum black (and crystallisation of the resulting product out of toluene), the hydro-derivative was obtained in quantitative yield as long colourless silky needles melting sharply at 57-58°. When oxidised with potassium permanganate in acetone solution hydrobhilawanol gave in good yield an acid, which was identified as palmitic acid. This proved bhilawanol to contain a single, normal, unsaturated C_{15} -side-chain, attached to a catechol nucleus. To fix

the position of this side-chain we oxidised diacetylphilawanol with permanagnate in acetone solution, and succeeded in obtaining an acid which on hydrolysis gave the colour reactions of 1:2:3-catecholcarboxylic acid.

The melting point of hydrophilawanol and the isolation of palmitic acid from its oxidation products suggested to us the possibility of its being identical with hydrourushiol ($C_{21}H_{36}O_2$), which was obtained by Majima and co-workers on hydrogenation of urushiol, the chief constituent of Japan lacquer, *Ki-urushi*, the dried juice of *Rhus vernicifera*, (*Ber.*, 1922, 55, 172 and preceding papers). This view was further supported by our obtaining both a mono- and a dinitro-product from the dimethyl ether after Majima (*Ber.*, 1913, 46, 4080) who found out that only 1:2:3- and not 1:2:4-catechol derivatives of this type yield a dinitro-product. We may note in this connection, however, that the nitric acid (d 1.52) recommended in the reference invariably gave only oily oxidation products and nitric acid (d 1.48) had to be used in order to get the crystalline dinitro-derivative.

The identity of hydrophilawanol and hydrourushiol was finally established by the fact that the melting points of hydrophilawanol and its dibenzoate and dimethyl ether derivatives, prepared by us, showed no depression when mixed with the corresponding derivatives of hydrourushiol, very kindly sent to us by Dr. Riko Majima of Japan.

Majima and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) have conclusively shown after an exhaustive examination of urushiol that it is a mixture of compounds, which differ from one another only in the number and position of the double bonds contained in the normal carbon side-chain, and which it is not possible to separate with the help of chemical methods at our command at present, but that in so far as this mixture gives a single chemical individual, hydro-urushiol, on reduction, it is quite legitimate to keep to the name urushiol for this mixture as well as the general molecular formula $C_{21}H_{32}O_2$, for convenience of reference. In consideration of these findings and taking into account the difference in the physical characteristics of urushiol (b.p. $200-10^\circ/5$ mm.; $d_4^{21.5} = 0.9687$; $n_D^{30} = 1.5234$) and philawanol (b.p. $213-14^\circ/1$ mm.; $d_4^{30} = 0.9542$; $n_D^{30} = 1.5032$), particularly the strikingly constant boiling point of the latter, we hold that while hydrophilawanol and hydrourushiol are fully identical chemical individuals, philawanol itself is of slightly

different and more uniform character than urushiol, which contains about 10 per cent. of hydrourushiol ($C_{21}H_{36}O_2$) along with the *o*-dihydroxy-compounds, answering to the general formulae, $C_{21}H_{34}O_2$, $C_{21}H_{32}O_2$ and probably also $C_{21}H_{30}O_2$ (*Ber.*, 1922, 55, 175). Indeed, it may be due to its greater uniformity that bhilawanol congealed below 5° to a fatty mass and that we easily obtained a solid naphthylurethane of bhilawanol, while urushiol failed to give any solid derivative.

Semecarpol.—The quantity of this phenol was so small that we could not undertake its detailed examination. It was, however, proved that it is distinct from bhilawanol, by means of reduction, whereby a crystalline hydrogenated product was obtained, which melted at $51-52^\circ$, and showed a large depression in its melting point when mixed with hydrobhilawanol. Its monophenolic character was established by determination of its hydroxyl content. Its analysis suggested the empirical formula, $C_{17}H_{28}O$, but as the product was too little to be sufficiently purified, the formula could not be definitely fixed upon.

From the tarry residue, left after distillation of bhilawanol, it was not possible to get any solid hydro-derivative on reduction. The elementary analysis of a purified fraction of it and determination of its molecular weight and hydroxyl content show that it is a mixture of high molecular resinous phenols having nearly the same empirical formula as bhilawanol. Subjected to destructive distillation it yielded a mixture of high-boiling phenols and hydrocarbons from which no catechol could be isolated, which would suggest the absence of catechol nucleus in the tarry products and form an argument against the tar being a mere polymer of bhilawanol, because the products of dry distillation of the latter contain catechol as the chief phenolic constituent. Majima got a similar corrosive residue after distillation of urushiol from *Ki-urushi* and suggested that it was the product of polymerisation of urushiol, but this does not appear probable because like bhilawanol, urushiol also is not observed by Majima to show any tendency towards polymerisation on subsequent distillation.

In reference to Naidu's (*loc. cit.*) investigations, we have to note that while we have found catechol to be absent as such in juice of the pericarp, it could be isolated from the products of decomposition of bhilawanol, and that from the account he has given of the isolation of what he describes as anacardol, we feel justified in suspecting that it was a product of decomposition. This

would explain his failure to get bhilawanol, which constitutes nearly half the ethereal extract, as well as his low yields, the difficulty he finds in freeing the high-boiling anacardol from catechol and his failure to get a proper acetyl derivative.

Apparently the most interesting feature of our investigation is the parallel established between the active constituents of *Semecarpus anacardium*, Linn and *Rhus vernicifera*, which belong to the same natural order (*Anacardiaceae*), but are put to totally different uses in their native countries, for, as is evident from the reference on *Ki-urushi*, it is not reputed for any medicinal properties in Japan. Apart from the scientific interest involved in our results, they may also extend the utility of each plant beyond its present dimensions and open up possibilities of establishing *bhilawan* as a valuable addition to the list of the natural products used in lacquer industry.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The material used for our investigations was obtained from the local bazaar. The crushed pericarp on extraction with ether yielded 28 to 36 per cent. of a dark brown oily extract having $d_{20}^{20} = 0.9603$.

Absence of Catechol in the Extract.—The extract (500 g.) was shaken four times with 200 c.c. each of water. The aqueous layer on very careful examination was found to contain no catechol but a trace of bhilawanol in suspension which gave a faint green coloration with ferric chloride.

Anacardic acid and cardol, the constituents of the juice of the cashew nut were tested for with freshly precipitated lead hydroxide according to the method of Ruhemann and Skinner (*Ber.*, 1887, 20, 1861) and were found to be absent.

Distillation in high vacuum was found to be the best method for the separation of the constituents of the extract. As a result of repeated fractional distillation below 3 mm. the following products were obtained.

Fraction 1.—A light yellow liquid boiling at 135-90°/2.5 mm. which congeals to a white fatty mass below 25° and forms only 0.1 per cent. of the total extract.

Fraction 2.—A golden yellow, slightly viscous liquid, boiling at 225-26°/3 mm. which forms about 46 per cent. of the weight of extract or 15 per cent. of the weight of the entire nut.

Residue.—A tarry non-volatile, dark brown, corrosive residue which forms 54 per cent. of the extract and 18 per cent. of the entire nut.

Examination of the Different Products.

Fraction 1: Semecarpol.—This fraction gives a white precipitate on the addition of alcoholic lead acetate and unlike Fraction 2, a fairly permanent green coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride indicating an *ortho*-phenol. On hydrogenation in absolute alcoholic solution in presence of platinum black according to the method of Willstätter (*Ber.*, 1908, **41**, 1475) a white solid was obtained, which when crystallised from ethyl acetate melted at 51-52° and showed a large depression of m.p. when mixed with hydrobhilawanol. (Found: C, 81.5; H, 11.3. $C_{17}H_{28}O$ requires C, 82.2; H, 11.3 per cent.). Estimated according to the method of Hibbert and Sudborough (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, **85**, 933), it gave a hydroxyl content of 7.4% (one hydroxyl requires 6.9%). 0.234 G. of the substance titrated against bromine in dry chloroform solution in a freezing mixture took up 0.162 g. of bromine (calc. for 1 double bond, 0.151 g.).

Fraction 2: Bhilawanol.—This fraction, has the following physical constants: B. p. 225-26°/3 mm. ; 213°-14°/1 mm. ; $d_{30}^{30} = 0.9591$

$$n_D^{30} = 1.5032; \quad \alpha_D^{30} = \text{nil.}$$

It congeals to a white fatty mass below 5°; with alcoholic ferric chloride it gives an evanescent green coloration, turning immediately to a black precipitate, and a violet-red coloration on further addition of a drop of alcoholic potash, indicating an *o*-dihydroxy-compound. With alcoholic lead acetate it gives a white precipitate which dissolves in ether with a green coloration. With caustic soda it gives a green phenolate insoluble in water but soluble in alcohol and ether, which darkens quickly on exposure to air due to oxidation. [Found: C, 79.8, 79.7; H, 10.7, 10.75. M. W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 345.3, 339.1. $C_{21}H_{32}O_2$ requires C, 79.8; H, 10.1 per cent. M. W., 316]. The hydroxyl content determined according to the method of Hibbert and Sudborough (*loc. cit.*) gave OH, 10.17, 10.24 (calc. for 2 OH, 10.7 per cent.).

Bromine-addition Product.—Bhilawanol (1.2 g.) titrated in dry cooled chloroform solution against bromine took up 1.16 g. (calc. for 2 double bonds, 1.21 g. bromine). Owing to the brownish-red

colour of the product the titration was followed by means of potassium iodide-starch paper. The product, obtained on evaporation as a brown syrup, could neither be distilled nor obtained as a solid.

Bhilawanol diacetate was prepared by boiling bhilawanol (12 g.) with acetic anhydride (16 g.) in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate and was obtained as a yellow liquid (10.5 g.) b. p. 230°/2 mm.; $d_{30}^{30}=0.9822$; $n_D^{30}=1.4822$. It has a characteristic smell and does not react with lead acetate or ferric chloride, showing the absence of hydroxyl groups. (Found: C, 74.8; H, 9.3. $C_{25}H_{36}O_4$ requires C, 75.0; H, 9.0 per cent.).

Bhilawanol dimethyl ether was prepared by treatment of bhilawanol with methyl iodide and sodium ethylate in absolute alcohol in a hydrogen atmosphere and was obtained as a mobile light yellow liquid, b. p. 218°/3.5 mm.; $d_{30}^{30}=0.9325$; $n_D^{30}=1.4896$. (Found: C, 80.1; H, 10.8. $C_{23}H_{36}O_2$ requires C, 80.2; H, 10.4 per cent.).

Bhilawanol dinaphthylurethane was obtained by treating bhilawanol (1.1 g.) with naphthyl isocyanate (1.13 g.) and dissolving the solid reaction product in hot alcohol from which it came down on cooling as a white powder melting at 138-40° (yield, 1.7 g.). (Found: N, 4.7. $C_{43}H_{46}O_4N_2$ requires N, 4.3 per cent.).

Distillation of Bhilawanol at Ordinary Pressure.

Bhilawanol (22 g.) subjected to dry distillation yielded 12.5 g. of total distillate, about 1 g. of which was found to be water. The remainder was separated by shaking in a hydrogen atmosphere with caustic soda solution into (a) phenols (3.5 g.) and (b) non-phenols (7.5 g.).

(a) *Phenols* obtained by the acidification of the caustic soda solution were fractionated. The first fraction boiling between 230° and 260° (1.3 g.) solidified. On crystallisation from benzene it gave crystals (0.7 g.) melting at 104° and identified as catechol by mixed melting point method. (Found: C, 65.05; H, 5.42. $C_6H_6O_2$ requires C, 65.42; H, 5.4 per cent.).

(b) *Non-phenols* were fractionated and the chief fraction boiling at 245-48° (1.8 g.) analysed, the results indicating a hydrocarbon. (Found: C, 85.38; H, 13.48 per cent.).

Oxidation of Bhilawanol Diacetate.—The substance (3.2 g.) was dissolved in a mixture of acetone (100 c.c.) and water (30 c.c.) and

acetic acid (6 c.c.) and then powdered potassium permanganate (8 g.) in small quantities at a time was added to the solution. Worked up in the usual manner, it yielded 2.1 g. of acids, which were hydrolysed with alcoholic potash in a hydrogen atmosphere. The resulting acids (1.7 g.) were not obtained solid, but gave the colour reactions of *o*-catechuic acid. A large-scale oxidation was not conducted as it was rendered unessential by our identifying hydrobhilawanol with hydrourushiol.

Catalytic Reduction of Bhilawanol.—To a solution of bhilawanol (3.5 g.) in absolute alcohol (6 c.c.) was added 1 g. of platinum black prepared according to the method of Willstätter and Mayer (*Ber.*, 1903, 41, 1475, 2199) and the mixture was placed in a closed bottle attached to a hydrogen generator and shaken in a shaking machine. The absorption of hydrogen ceased in five hours. The resulting product, when filtered from the platinum black and freed of the solvent on the water-bath, gave the hydro-product as a crystalline solid. On recrystallisation from toluene hydrobphilawanol was obtained as white needles (3.2 g.) melting at 57–58°. (Found: C, 78.43; H, 11.60. $C_{21}H_{36}O_2$ requires C, 78.62; H, 11.32 per cent.).

Oxidation of Hydrobphilawanol: Palmitic Acid.—To hydrobhilawanol (2.2 g.) dissolved in acetone (200 c.c.) and water (30 c.c.) was added a solution of potassium permanganate (7 g.) in acetone (200 c.c.) and water (30 c.c.). The mixture was warmed until decolourised and filtered. From the filtrate acetone was removed on a water-bath and the aqueous residue acidified with hydrochloric acid. The acid thereby liberated (1.05 g.) after two crystallisations out of 95% alcohol melted at 59–60°, the melting point showing no depression on admixture with a sample of pure palmitic acid.

Diacetyl Hydrobphilawanol.—It was prepared by acetylation of hydrobphilawanol with acetic anhydride and anhydrous sodium acetate and was obtained as shining white plates; from alcohol, m.p. 51°.

Dibenzoyl hydrobphilawanol was prepared by treating hydrobhilawanol (0.5 g.) in dry ether (5 c.c.) with benzoyl chloride (1 g.) and working up the reaction product in the usual manner. On crystallisation out of alcohol the dibenzoate melted at 59–60°.

The *dimethyl ether* prepared by the reduction of bhilawanol dimethyl ether (2 g.) in ethereal solution in presence of platinum black, melted at 36–37°, when crystallised out of alcohol (1.8 g.).

The melting points of hydrobhilawanol and its two last mentioned derivatives showed no depression on admixture with the corresponding derivatives of urushiol.

Mononitrohydrobphilawanol Methyl Ether.—Hydrobphilawanol dimethyl ether (0.8 g.) in glacial acetic acid (3 c.c.) was treated with a mixture of nitric acid (d 1.48, 3 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (5 c.c.). The mixture was warmed for half a minute on the water-bath and then kept aside to cool. The resulting yellow crystals when crystallised from alcohol gave 0.4 g. of light yellow needles, m.p. 71-72°.

Dinitrohydrobphilawanol Dimethyl Ether.—The mononitro-derivative (0.5 g.) was treated with nitric acid (d 1.48, 1 c.c.), warmed for 2 minutes on the water-bath until it dissolved and then quickly cooled and diluted. The dinitro-derivative, which separated out as a solid, crystallised out of alcohol in light yellow needles melting at 83°.

The Tarry Residue.—This forms more than 50% of the ether extract and was obtained after the distillation of bhilawanol as a very viscous dark mass. It was purified by dissolving in 80% cold alcohol, which leaves a thick dark resinous mass undissolved, treating the alcoholic solution with lead acetate and liberating the tarry phenolic product from the lead salt with hydrochloric acid. It dissolves in alcoholic potash with a fairly permanent grass-green coloration. With ferric chloride it gives a very transient green colour followed by a black precipitate. With lead acetate it forms a green precipitate. It was found that it could be acetylated and etherified just like bhilawanol, but none of the products could be distilled or made to solidify even when hydrogenated. On distillation at ordinary pressure the tar (20 g.) gave a mixture of phenols (2.7 g.) and non-phenols (3 g.) but no catechol was obtained from the distillate. The M. W. found by the depression of the freezing point of benzene was nearly 1000. Its reactions indicate that it is a mixture of high molecular resinous phenols but it could not be further investigated owing to the impossibility of purifying it or its derivatives. (Found: C, 78.74; H, 10.09. $(C_{21}H_{32}O_2)_n$ requires C, 79.8; H, 10.1 per cent.)

In conclusion we heartily thank Dr. Riko Majima of Japan for kindly providing us with samples of hydrourushiol and two of its derivatives.

